

THE ELECTRON MICROSCOPY DATA PROCESSING PORTAL: A NEW CAPABILITY FOR DATA-INTENSIVE RESEARCH

*WORK PACKAGE 4: BIG-DATA ELECTRON AND
CORRELATIVE MICROSCOPY FROM
INSTRUMENT TO PUBLICATION*

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The Electron Microscopy Data Processing Portal: A new capability for data-intensive research

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Executive summary

The Electron Microscopy Data Processing Portal has been deployed to provide a capability for data-intensive research. The Portal has been developed by the "Big-data electron and correlative microscopy from instrument to publication" team in the Australian Characterisation Commons at Scale (ACCS) project as an effective tool for processing cryogenic electron microscopy data using the software CryoSPARC and LiberTEM.

Deploying new national infrastructure is challenging. This report presents the approach taken and the challenges of deploying this Portal as a cloud-based national service.

Introduction

In recent years the number of cryogenic electron microscopy (Cryo-EM) instruments has increased in Australia and internationally. In parallel to this, so has the demand for storage and compute capability to support the processing of the large datasets produced by these instruments.

Relion¹ and CryoSPARC² are amongst the main software products focused on processing CryoEM data. CryoSPARC was previously identified as an effective tool within the Work Package 4 document *Orchestration and management of data generated by big-data electron microscopy instruments: A Discovery report*.³ For many users CryoSPARC is becoming a suitable platform for processing the majority of CryoEM datasets. A key recommendation of the report was to increase the availability of compute for CryoSPARC and LiberTEM⁴ to users.

¹ https://www3.mrc-lmb.cam.ac.uk/relion/index.php/Main_Page

² <https://cryosparc.com/>

³ <https://osf.io/4k6xq/>

⁴ <https://libertem.github.io/LiberTEM/>

The ACCS (Australian Characterisation Commons at Scale) provided funding for compute hardware to be purchased for the EM Community with the requirement to develop a national service for CryoSPARC and LiberTEM. This service will be known as the 'EM Data Processing Portal'. The hardware is managed at the Nectar⁵ nodes 'QRISCloud' managed by QCIF (Queensland Cyber Infrastructure Foundation) in Brisbane and 'Monash-02' managed by MeRC (Monash University eResearch Centre) in Melbourne.

In this report, the deployment of this national service is described. Wherever possible existing software has been leveraged to ease the deployment process. Globus was chosen for data movement as experience in deploying it had already been obtained earlier in the ACCS project under *Work Package 4.1: Investigate, prototype, and deploy a higher-level transport service data transport*. Experience in deploying four CryoSPARC servers on MASSIVE was also leveraged.

This work was undertaken under the Australian Characterisation Commons at Scale (ACCS) project, in particular under Work Package 4: "Big-data electron and correlative microscopy from instrument to publication". This report is intended as the conclusion of the work planned for deliverable WP4.7: "Make EM software more accessible to users".

Description of CryoSPARC

CryoSPARC is developed by Structura Biotechnology in Toronto, Canada. This is a commercial software product, however the licensing agreement allows for free usage by non-profit researchers. CryoSPARC was originally released in 2017 and has grown to be very popular among the biological Cryo-EM community.

On MASSIVE there are currently four instances of CryoSPARC running on dedicated nodes. Over time, a large amount of experience has been obtained on how to successfully run CryoSPARC in a multi-user environment such as a HPC (High Performance Computing). CryoSPARC consists of two main software components. The *cryosparc_master* runs as a web server which manages user accounts, provides a login interface, cli (command line interface) and runs some jobs. The *cryosparc_worker* mainly handles any jobs requiring GPU processing. CryoSPARC can be installed in two different modes: *standalone* or *cluster*. *Standalone* installations assume that all accessible GPUs (Graphical Processing Units) are on the one machine. *Cluster* provides support to access many compute nodes, thus enabling access to more GPUs than a single machine can provide. A *cluster* installation can be configured to submit jobs to a HPC scheduling system such as Slurm.

Most of the CryoSPARC services on MASSIVE are *standalone* installations. Given that MASSIVE is a multi-user environment, this provides challenges with regards to data ownership, as CryoSPARC runs under a single user account. CryoSPARC contains its own user management system, however it is not possible to configure it to be aware of the HPC user management system. This creates data access challenges for users who wish to obtain their

⁵ <https://ardc.edu.au/services/ardc-nectar-research-cloud/>

data from within CryoSPARC. Access Control Lists (ACLs) have provided a work around for this.

An alternative method is to deploy CryoSPARC per user, running under the user's own account ID, as it resolves the data ownership challenge. This is the approach adopted for the 'EM Data Processing Portal'.

Description of LiberTEM

LiberTEM is an open source platform available from Github⁶. The majority of the code was developed by Alexander Clausen from the Jülich Research Centre and Ernst Ruska Centre in Germany. LiberTEM allows the 'EM Data Processing Portal' to support the wider microscopy community for data processing, in particular in the field of materials science

LiberTEM has been installed on the shared file system of the EM Data Processing Portal. It runs as a web accessible application once started.

Deployment of the EM Data Processing Portal in Nectar

A single Nectar project was created to contain all the compute hardware and storage from the Monash-02 and QRIS CLOUD availability zones. Deployment of the portal for both availability zones has been performed by staff from the Monash eResearch Centre. Wherever possible tools and technologies have been reused to aid in delivering the service. To build a sustainable service, automation is a must due to limited human resources available for implementing, managing and running the service.

Deployment of the hardware and software for both availability zones (Monash-02 and QRIS CLOUD) has been built upon an Ansible⁷ based repository known as HPCasCode. (<https://gitlab.erc.monash.edu.au/hpc-team/HPCasCode>) Ansible is a technology for automating deployment of hardware and software in a cloud environment such as Nectar. The repository HPCasCode, is used to manage the MASSIVE HPC system. The HPCasCode repository was cloned and initially configured to deploy a basic compute cluster consisting of a bastion node, for administration access; two login nodes for user access and to run SLURM; one node for the SLURM database and network file system server; one globus node for data movement and the compute nodes. This configuration was adopted from a similarly built cluster to run a National Machine Learning service, known as MLeRP - Machine Learning eResearch Platform (<https://mlerp.cloud.edu.au/>)

The compute hardware, deployed as virtual machines (VMs), consists of 12x NVIDIA A100 GPUs with 40 GB memory, this is per cluster, so a total of 24 GPUs have been deployed

⁶ <https://github.com/LiberTEM>

⁷ www.ansible.com

across the Monash-02 and QRIS CLOUD availability zones. For CryoSPARC, 40 GB of GPU memory is excessive. Using a new technology known as Multi-Instance-GPU⁸ (MIG), each GPU has been split into 3 GPUS, 2 with 10GB and 1 with 20 GB of video memory. This is still a very generous amount of memory for CryoSPARC processing. This effectively created 36 GPUs at each site. To support the deployment of MIG, two Ansible roles, 'nvidia_mig_configure'⁹ and 'nvidia_mig_tools'¹⁰ were amended to ensure the MIG configuration persisted after a machine reboot and so a user-defined version of NVIDIA CUDA¹¹ could be deployed. CryoSPARC v3.3.2 officially supports CUDA version 11.2. CUDA is how CryoSPARC accesses the GPU for processing.

After initial deployment of the cluster, it was discovered that SLURM was unable to access the MIG configured GPUs. The SLURM version 21.08.8 or later is required to detect MIG configured GPUs. This was updated and the clusters redeployed.

Deploying CryoSPARC

The advice obtained from the CryoSPARC development team was to run a single instance of CryoSPARC per user on the cluster. This approach avoids all the file ownership challenges experienced with running a multi-user CryoSPARC instance on MASSIVE. Initially there was discussion about CryoSPARC supplying a pool of licences, however this did not eventuate and it was decided that end-users should obtain and supply their own licence so that CryoSPARC could be installed into their own user account.

For testing purposes, CryoSPARC was deployed and configured to ensure it was able to submit jobs to the SLURM cluster and execute correctly on the MIG configured GPUs. For all the *cryosparc_worker* jobs, SLURM would handle the scheduling and sharing of resources, but the next problem to solve was how to manage the compute resources required for *cryosparc_master*. After investigation and testing, a SLURM script was developed to run the *cryosparc_master* as a SLURM job. The *cryosparc_master* consists of a web server and a database. Databases need to be cleanly shutdown, not terminated as can happen when a SLURM job reaches its wall time. Terminating a database can possibly corrupt it. To run the *cryosparc_master* as a SLURM job and to ensure clean shutdown of the database, a 'signal' was configured with an accompanying function to cleanly shut down the database. When the job is running a 'signal' is sent by SLURM to the running job, just before it completes. The signal is then detected, and a user configurable action can take place, in this case 'cryosparcm stop'.

⁸ <https://docs.nvidia.com/datacenter/tesla/mig-user-guide/>

⁹ https://gitlab.erc.monash.edu.au/hpc-team/HPCasCode/-/tree/master/roles/nvidia_mig_configure

¹⁰ https://gitlab.erc.monash.edu.au/hpc-team/HPCasCode/-/tree/master/roles/nvidia_mig_tools

¹¹ <https://developer.nvidia.com/cuda-toolkit>

There were two more issues to resolve due to running *cryosparc_master* as a SLURM job: the hostname and the port number. The combination of both the hostname and port number needs to be unique for each *cryosparc_master*. To maximise the use of the compute resources, multiple *cryosparc_masters* would be run on each compute node. The hostname would change based on which compute node SLURM scheduled the job and also the port that CryoSPARC would run on. The script that runs *cryosparc_master* was altered to update the hostname in the file, 'config.sh'. A helper program¹² was written to check the availability of the port number on the compute node. This is executed, and then the command 'cryosparcm changeport' was used to set the available port and start CryoSPARC. The compute resources required to run CryoSPARC can now be fully managed by SLURM.

To contribute to the goal of automating the service, a SLURM script was developed to perform the installation of CryoSPARC into the user's account, fully configured with a user account in CryoSPARC and for submitting worker jobs to the cluster. The required inputs to the script are: licence ID, email address, first name and last name and password.

Testing CryoSPARC

After development of the SLURM scripts to install and run CryoSPARC, a full test was warranted. A clean installation was performed on the QRIS CLOUD cluster using the installation script and then the start job was submitted to SLURM. To test CryoSPARC, there is an automated workflow¹³ that downloads a dataset and then runs through an extensive list of data analysis. Initial impression was that the installation was very slow compared to MASSIVE.

Running the automated workflow failed as the main process timed out waiting for a sub process to complete. After raising this on the CryoSPARC discussion forum, a reply suggested there was a storage performance issue. The only way the automated workflow would run entirely was to amend the code and increase the timeout period from 120 second to 360.

To investigate the performance issue, the same test was performed on the cluster at Monash-02. The installation of CryoSPARC was faster and the automated workflow ran to completion. Two clusters, same deployment and configuration, differing performance. The timeout experienced on the QRIS CLOUD cluster required further investigation to ensure a workable service would be delivered.

¹² <https://gitlab.erc.monash.edu.au/hpc-team/portchecker>

¹³

<https://guide.cryosparc.com/setup-configuration-and-management/software-guides/tutorial-verify-cryosparc-installation-with-the-extensive-workflow-sysadmin-guide>

Deployment of Globus for data movement

With the performance issue under consideration, it was decided to deploy and test Globus¹⁴ for data movement on the QRISCLOUD cluster. Globus was chosen as it can perform data transfer at high speed between physically distant systems, ideal for a national service. Prior experience with Globus was also obtained from the ACCS Work Package 4.1 deliverable. Initially the plan was to leverage the previously developed Ansible roles for Globus deployment.¹⁵ However, since the roles were developed, changes made to Globus prevented their use. The Ansible roles still provide a good summary of the required steps and Globus was manually installed. After deploying and logging into Globus.org, the endpoint did not respond when trying to connect to it. Globus.org reported a timeout. The 'globus-connect-server self-diagnostic' command was run to check the installation and system logging was investigated. Nothing was found that would explain the timeout.

A ticket was raised with Globus support. With regular responses, over more than a week, a great deal of knowledge was gained in the process of debugging Globus, however the conclusion ended up being there was a problem with the machine itself, not the Globus installation. The quality of support from Globus is to be commended. While communication with Globus took place, the storage performance at QRISCLOUD was investigated. To further investigate, the same Globus deployment was performed on the 'Monash-02' cluster. Access from Globus.org was successful, however, testing the next day also failed with the same timeout as experienced with the QRISCLOUD deployment. No changes had been made after the initial deployment, more investigation was required.

Performance testing of compute nodes and storage

To gain some metrics, the CryoSPARC installation script was modified to capture the run time on QRISCLOUD, Monash-02 and MASSIVE.

<u>Availability zone, storage tested.</u>	<u>Time to install and configure CryoSPARC.</u>
QRISCLOUD volume storage (nfs mounted) on a compute node.	3258 seconds
Monash-02 volume storage (nfs mounted) on a compute node	2176 seconds
MASSIVE - /scratch (Lustre), run on m3p001 node	533 seconds

¹⁴ <https://www.globus.org/>

¹⁵ <https://github.com/Characterisation-Virtual-Laboratory/Globus-Endpoint-deployment>

Obtaining the installation time of CryoSPARC, was viewed as an easily run common test between the different systems. The installation involves downloading the cryosparc master and worker tarballs, expanding them, running an executable that then configures CryoSPARC which includes installing Conda and a large number of Python packages, starting CryoSPARC to configure a user, configuring the worker and then stopping CryoSPARC. The above table highlights the performance issue experienced at QRIS CLOUD, with Monash-02 being an improvement but not fast compared to MASSIVE.

For the initial deployment of the cluster, the SLURM database and the Network File System (NFS) Server were on the same machine, a Nectar flavour of m3.small with 2 CPUs and 4 GB RAM. Clearly, not enough resources to run a database and an NFS server for a powerful compute cluster. This machine was reconfigured to an m3.xlarge with 16 CPUs and 32 GB RAM. To check for any improvement the same installation script was re-run.

<u>Availability zone, storage tested.</u>	<u>Time to install and configure CryoSPARC.</u>
QRIS CLOUD volume storage (nfs mounted) on a compute node.	2942 seconds

Unfortunately, increasing the amount of compute for the NFS server did not yield the expected performance improvement.

Since the compute cluster has several different types of storage (e.g. local nvme, nfs mounted volume storage, Nectar mounted volume storage), rsync was used to move data between the various types to test the network but to also hopefully highlight where the performance bottleneck was located. The dataset used was the actual CryoSPARC installation.

Source (machine - storage)	Destination (machine - storage)	Speed	Note:
gerp-qcif-sql0 - mounted volume storage	gerp-qcif-sql0 - mounted volume storage	23,682,455.49 bytes/sec	rsync on the same machine to the same storage
gerp-qcif-sql0 - mounted volume storage	gerp-qcif-node00 - nvme	21,568,032.47 bytes/sec	rsync to nvme on another machine. A bit slower but using the network between machines.
gerp-qcif-node00 - nvme	gerp-qcif-node00 - nfs mounted volume storage	3,319,455.77 bytes/sec	rsync on the same machine from nvme to nfs mounted

			storage.
gerp-qcif-node0 - nvme	gerp-qcif-node01 - nvme	145,267,517.41 bytes/sec	rsync between compute nodes, nvme to nvme.

Finally a clue as to where the issue is. The NFS mounted volume storage is supporting only 3 MB/sec vs 23 MB/sec. So, the question to answer is, why is the NFS mounted storage performing so badly ?

Not being an expert in NFS, some investigation was required. NFS performance tuning steps were investigated, but unfortunately, these yielded no improvement. Is there something in the underlying network causing this issue ?

The Network configuration.

After contacting a member of the Research Cloud team at the Monash eResearch Centre, a discussion around network configuration took place.

The below diagram shows how the network was configured for each cluster.

The key points from this diagram are the floating IPs applied to the bastion, login and Globus nodes, and the use of an internally configured private network. The Research Cloud team advised the removal of the private network and the floating IP addresses. These two network features are considered advanced networking in the Nectar Research Cloud and are

implemented using software defined networking that was setup to be functional but with no emphasis placed on performance.

Below is the final network implementation. Each machine now has a public IP address, using the 'Classic Provider' interface in Nectar terminology. The SQL database required by SLURM and the Network File System server have been separated onto their own virtual machines. Advice was provided, that the database would over time consume system memory impacting the NFS server. Without the internal private network all nodes of the cluster were now accessible on the public internet. This is not ideal from a security point of view. To address security concerns, Nectar security groups have been configured to restrict access. The 'cluster-sec-group' was configured so that only machines in that grouping could access each other on port 22. This prevents public access to the compute nodes, sql0 and nfs server. The 'globus-sec-group' was unchanged, allowing public access via ports 80, 443 and 50000 to 51000. The last one, 'bastion-sec-group' was configured to allow public access via port 22. This was added to the bastion and login nodes.

Both compute clusters at QRISLOUD and Monash-02 were redeployed with this network configuration.

Re-testing compute and storage performance

After redeploying both clusters with the new network configuration, CryoSPARC was reinstalled, and Globus retested.

Globus on QRISLOUD was functional, no timeout was received. A test data transfer from the collection 'AARNet Readonly Public Test Share' using a dataset of 500 GB with large files to

'EM Data Processing Portal at QCIF' yielded a transfer rate of 317.49 MB/s. This was a vast improvement for a previously unusable system.

On QRISCLOUD, CryoSPARC was reinstalled and the automated test workflow started. This time no timeout occurred and the workflow completed successfully.

The intermittency experienced with accessing the Globus collection 'EM Data Processing Portal at MeRC' was also resolved.

Deploying LiberTEM

Compared to the challenges involved with deploying CryoSPARC and resolving the performance issues, LiberTEM was very easy to install and configure. The installation instructions detailed in the code repository (<https://libertem.github.io/LiberTEM/>) were followed.

Initial testing has been completed. Further testing will take place with a member from the electron microscopy community to ensure the software is functioning properly.

Compute resource configuration

This section of the report focuses on the available compute resources and how many instances of CryoSPARC can be supported, which leads into how the resources were configured to support them.

A summary of the recommended hardware requirements for the CryoSPARC master and work processes¹⁶.

CryoSPARC master

Component	Minimum	Recommended
CPU	4+ cores	8+ cores
RAM	16GB+	32GB
GPU	Not required	Not required

CryoSPARC worker

¹⁶

<https://guide.cryosparc.com/setup-configuration-and-management/hardware-and-system-requirements/#cryosparc-system-requirements>

Component	Minimum	Recommended
CPU	2+ cores per GPU	4+ cores per GPU
RAM	32GB+ per GPU	64GB per GPU
GPU	1+	1+

QRISCLOUD configuration

At QRISCLOUD, twelve compute nodes were deployed using the flavour 'qld.64c600g.A100.nvme'. Each GPU was then configured using Multi-Instance-GPU (MIG), to provide a compute node with these specifications.

```
qld.64c600g.A100.nvme
- 64 CPUs
- 600 GB RAM
- 1 x A100 40 GB, with MIG - 2 x 10GB, 1 x 20 GB, therefore 3 GPUs
- SSD NVME 3.6 TB
```

Due to the use of MIG, effectively 3 GPUs are available per compute node. Assuming 1 GPU per CryoSPARC instance and referring to the above hardware requirements. For each compute node:

Based on minimum requirements	Based on recommended requirements
3 CryoSPARC Masters - 3 x 4 = 12 CPUs - 3 x 16 = 48 GB	3 CryoSPARC Masters - 3 x 8 = 24 CPUs - 3 x 32 = 96 GB
3 CryoSPARC Workers - 3 x 2 = 6 CPUs - 3 x 32 = 96 GB	3 CryoSPARC Workers - 3 x 4 = 12 CPUs - 3 x 64 = 192 GB
Totals: - 18 CPUs - 144 GB RAM	Totals: - 36 CPUs - 288 GB RAM

Each compute node can comfortably run 3 CryoSPARC instances at the recommended specifications, giving a total of 36 CryoSPARC instances across the 12 compute nodes.

Monash-02 configuration

At Monash-02, the compute nodes were deployed using the flavours:

- mon.c52r460.2gpu-A100.numa
- mon.c52r920.2gpu-A100.numa

Each GPU was then configured using Multi-Instance-GPU (MIG), to provide compute nodes with these specifications.

mon.c52r460.2gpu-A100.numa

- 52 CPUs
- 460 GB RAM
- 2 x A100 40 GB, with MIG - 4 x 10GB, 2 x 20 GB, therefore 6 GPUs
- SSD NVME ?? TB

mon.c52r920.2gpu-A100.numa

- 52 CPUs
- 920 GB RAM
- 2 x A100 40 GB, with MIG - 4 x 10GB, 2 x 20 GB, therefore 6 GPUs
- SSD NVME ?? TB

Again, due to the use of MIG, effectively 6 GPUs are available per compute node. Assuming 1 GPU per CryoSPARC instance and referring to the above hardware requirements. For each compute node:

Based on minimum requirements	Based on recommended requirements
6 CryoSPARC Masters - 6 x 4 = 24 CPUs - 6 x 16 = 96 GB	6 CryoSPARC Masters - 6 x 8 = 48 CPUs - 6 x 32 = 192 GB
6 CryoSPARC Workers - 6 x 2 = 12 CPUs - 6 x 32 = 192 GB	6 CryoSPARC Workers - 6 x 4 = 24 CPUs - 6 x 64 = 384 GB
Totals: - 36 CPUs - 288 GB RAM	Totals: - 72 CPUs - 576 GB RAM

Each compute node has a total of 52 CPUs, which puts CryoSPARC between the minimum and recommended requirements for Monash-02. The nodes with 920 GB RAM, exceed the recommended memory requirements, but are restricted by the total of 52 CPUs.

Each compute node can run 6 CryoSPARC instances at better than the minimum specifications, giving a total of 36 CryoSPARC instances across the compute nodes.

SLURM configuration

For both of the clusters, to ensure SLURM spread the 'CPU' only *cryosparc_master* between compute nodes, a *cryosparc_master* partition was configured with `MaxCPUsPerNode=24`. This prevents SLURM from scheduling all the *cryosparc_master* jobs into one node. If this occurred there would not be enough CPUs available to drive the GPUs on the same node, effectively making the GPUs inaccessible.

For the QCIF cluster this restricts the *cryosparc_master* to only 3 per compute node as the job has been configured for 8 CPUs.

For the Monash cluster this restricts the *cryosparc_master* to only 6 per compute node as the job has been configured for 4 CPUs. (n.b. 2 GPUs per node for Monash, 1 GPU for node for QCIF)

Storage

To support data processing Nectar has supplied 50 TB of volume storage for each cluster.

Each compute cluster has been configured to provide 36 GPUs with enough compute resources to support running 36 instances of CryoSPARC.

Thanks to the feedback from the Users' Reference Group that provided advice on the configuration and conditions of use of CryoSPARC in the EM Data Processing Portal, it was estimated that CryoSPARC would require up to 3–4 TB of storage space. It was therefore decided to allocate each user a quota of 4.8 TB of working storage. This quota includes the CryoSPARC installation, primary (input) data for processing and processed data.

The amount of storage available supports 10 users on each cluster. At the time of writing, 7 beta users have been provisioned on the QCIF cluster.

Depending on user demand, more storage will be required to take full advantage of the total amount of processing resources available.

User provisioning and Strudel v2 Configuration

In deploying this service, and making it sustainable for the long term, the amount of administration required to run the service needed to be kept to a minimum. In order to do this we've leveraged "gitops" to manage allocations and provisioning of user accounts. Adding a new user or changing their allocated storage thus consists of approving a merge request via the web interface to gitlab. Because this is a matter of "clicking a button in a web browser" it can be delegated to non-technical service managers or performed with a minimum of overhead by technical team members.

The list of allocations is designed to be human readable and editable. During beta testing we are using a command line tool to quickly generate additional allocations. During production we may use an automated system for the user to request additional allocations directly (for example an automated signup form). If a user needs a non-standard resource allocation (e.g. they have a much larger data set and require additional quota) we are able to directly edit the human editable list of allocations.

Once an allocation is approved, a combination of automated tasks take over actual provisioning processes. The code used for provisioning, as well as generating additional allocations on the command line is provided as an open source repository:

https://gitlab.erc.monash.edu.au/hpc-team/gerp_provisioning

Resources

The code used to deploy the EM Data Processing Portal has been made available at: <https://github.com/Characterisation-Virtual-Laboratory/EM-Data-Processing-Portal>

This repository is a cleansed copy of the one used in production, however it contains all the important details and notes required to perform a full deployment of the system.

Outcome

The EM Data Processing Portal is now live and accessible to the community. Information on how to gain access and use the service is available on the Imaging Tools website - <https://imagingtools.au/em-data-processing-portal>

To promote the service to the wider community, an event has been organised (<https://imagingtools.au/events-calendar/em-data-processing-portal>). During this event the developer of the service and a beta tester will provide insights to the community and encourage usage.

Conclusion

Deployment of the EM Data Processing Portal has been challenging in several ways, but very rewarding in the knowledge and experience gained from deploying two high performance

clusters in Nectar. The limiting factor for the service is the amount of storage available, not the processing capability. It is hoped that user demand will exceed the storage capacity and a request to Nectar and the Australian Research Data Commons will be made for additional storage to make the service a long term success. If the expected demand for the service does not materialise, the surplus GPU nodes will be handed back to Nectar for use in other services, to ensure full use of the hardware.

Sustainability of the service, which has not been discussed in the report, is a challenge. The service has been built largely by a single person. There will be future discussions attempting to address sustainability between the involved parties.

Acknowledgement

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Contributorship

JvS designed the work, prototyped, tested and deployment of CryoSPARC in the SLURM cluster environment. CH designed and developed the user provisioning system and Strudel v2.

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